

Multilevel Governance Model for Enlarged Europe: Is Diversity Sustainable?

Vasile CUCERESCU

Abstract: European integration process has led to a change of governance paradigm in the European Union. Political participation and representation of various actors (institutions and citizens) in the democratic governance makes the European Union a unique legal and political entity in the world. Good governance implies multilevel governance, bringing together vertical supranational, national, regional and local actors with horizontal public and private actors for efficient organization of Europe's societies. European integration process finds out diversified governance practices, thus juxtaposing, interconnecting and influencing each other in shaping sustainable governance in enlarged Europe. Public and private – national, regional and local – actors are in the position to adapt themselves to new socio-political realities. Some of them succeed, oppose or fail, depending on socio-economic and political capabilities of joining countries. Associated countries face the same challenges as Europeanization of political and legal regulatory processes are inevitable. Multilevel governance requires multilevel regulation at supranational and national levels. Multilevel governance captures multilevel regulation and affects the quality of democracy. Multilevel governance is conducive indubitably to Europeanization *per se*. The focus is to examine legally and politically the behaviour of multilevel actors from Member States and associated countries, pointing out how diversity functions in this “melting pot”.

Keywords: *accountability, democracy, governance, legitimacy, representation.*

Introduction

During the last two decades multilevel governance has been widely discussed by scholars to elucidate its role in the European Union. Multilevel governance is directly linked to European integration process, especially legal and political integration. The Treaty of Maastricht (1992) determined generally the new approach towards governance in the

European Union with the move beyond economic concerns, approaching to political aspirations. In deepening European integration the Treaty of Maastricht follows five key goals: to strengthen the democratic legitimacy of the institutions; to improve the effectiveness of the institutions; to establish economic and monetary union; to develop the Community social dimension; to establish a common foreign and security policy.

The concept of multilevel governance is a theory in public administration and political science related to the study of European integration, namely the European Union. The developers of multilevel governance were Gary Marks and Liesbet Hooghe in the early 1990s. The theory of multilevel governance resulted on the legal grounds of the Treaty of Maastricht or, formally, the *Treaty on European Union* with the new structures of the European Union, which consists of three pillars: the European Communities, common foreign and security policy, and police and judicial cooperation in criminal matters. The European Union applied in practice multilevel governance due to the complexity of relations between different authorities at national and supranational levels. The Treaty establishes policies in six new areas for the European Union: trans-European networks; industrial policy; consumer protection; education and vocational training; youth; culture. The Treaty recognizes the importance of the regional dimension, by creating the Committee of the Regions, made up of the representatives of regional authorities with an advisory role.

The Treaty of Lisbon responded to the needs of enlarged European Union with 27 states. It means that the European Union had to adapt itself to new structural realities in terms of institutional functioning and decision-making, and, consequently, law-making. The Treaty of Lisbon redefined and strengthened EU policies. The Treaty of Lisbon contributed to reform European institutions and to improve the decision-making process; strengthen the democratic dimension of the European Union; reform the internal policies of the European Union; to strengthen the external policies of the European Union. The Treaty of Lisbon captures institutional issues, new voting procedures for decisions; citizens' initiative in the building of Europe; powers in such aspects as border control, asylum and immigration,

judicial cooperation in civil matters, judicial cooperation in criminal matters and police cooperation in creating the European area for freedom, security and justice; coherence and visibility for external policies of the European Union. A major concern refers to the Common Security and Defense Policy.

Gary Marks and Liesbet Hooghe challenged traditional state-centric views, sovereignty of Member States, application of decision-making, and powers of supranational institutions: “European states are losing their grip on the mediation of domestic interest representation in international relations”¹. In a later paper Gary Marks and Liesbet Hooghe stated that due to European integration “a multi-level polity has been created that delivers, or co-delivers, several of the chief outputs of government, including monetary policy, competition policy, regional policy, market regulation, and elements of industrial relations, law and order, and education”². In fact, the result is a complex process that involves numerous actors by vertical and horizontal dimensions. P. Stubbs mentions that “a multi-level governance perspective forces one to address processes of the supranationalisation, the decentralisation and the dispersal of authority as potentially coterminous, rather than engage in very narrow, linear, debates about the influence, or lack of influence, of international agencies”³. Later, professor J. McCormick noticed notably that “multilevel governance is a conceptual cousin of two other, older concepts”, federalism and confederalism⁴. Speaking about the impact of this theory in respect to European Union’s legislation, A. Wiener and T. Diez argued: “Although multilevel governance is discussed as a general attribute of European governance, it is perhaps most important for understanding the implementation of European directives”⁵. Following the waves of impact, it is worth mentioning the political consequences of European multilevel governance: “Multilevel governance empowers, or in some instances

¹ G. Marks and L. Hooghe (1996): 341

² Idem (2004): 1

³ P. Stubbs (2005): 67

⁴ J. McCormick (2008): 15

⁵ A. Wiener and T. Diez (2009): 95

virtually creates, regional entities with European member states. This empowerment may help to legitimate the EU, given that it involves and recognizes lower level governments which tend to have greater legitimacy (especially in multi-ethnic countries) than do national governments. In addition, the development of these relationships does provide some social and political groups which might have relatively little influence over policy in other circumstances”⁶.

There are shaped certain challenges for multilevel governance as any governance must be able to not only coordinate relevant actors at supranational, national, regional and local levels, but also achieve collective action rapidly enough to face newly appeared problems or on the way to emerge. All of them depend exclusively on the level of European integration process.

Paradigms and Theories of European integration

The integration process of Europe’s countries in the European Union is an important research topic in EU Law and EU studies. Approaches converge to two types of paradigms: the intergovernmental paradigm (theories that define the European Union as an agreement between the Member States, i.e. intergovernmentalism, transactionalism, consociationalism, etc.); and the supranational paradigm (theories that define a strong supranational European Union, i.e. functionalism, neo-functionalism, federalism, confederalism, etc.).

Coexistence of integration paradigms is explained by the fact that there are two opposing forces in the European integration process: “federalists” who wanted a speedy advancement as integration (D. Sidjanski referred to federalist vocation) and “nationalists” who preferred more intergovernmental cooperation rather than integration. The progress in European integration process exposed compromise between paradigms.

For effective information, the evolution of European integration was and is described in an accessible and linear manner, identifying distinct periods

⁶ Ibidem: 96

or phases of the process of European integration. Consequently, there have been various theories designed to explain the formal European integration (legal regulations) and informal European integration (common market and policies, agreed by enforcement of adopted mechanisms). For scientific and practical reasons, the evolution of European integration appears as an extremely complex process.

Promoting integration theories as principles of European integration process was done according to the contribution of political leaders who participated at one time or another in building a united Europe. Thus, they will be presented in terms of double approaches, formal and informal.

In the early days of European integration it was thought the best to focus on specific sectors of the economy with distinct functions to be managed effectively by supranational institutions and without political interference. As a result, there were established European Coal and Steel Community in 1951, and subsequently the European Atomic Energy Community in 1957. Promoters of European integration ideas are reflected by the functionalist theory (D. Mitrany).

With the creation of the European Economic Community in 1957, functionalism felt betrayed. The new community is reflected by the neo-functional theory (E. B. Haas), corresponding to an evolutionary, incrementalist, approach in terms of European integration where stimulation persists on supranational institutions created by the Member States. The theory is also known as the theory of European integration authorized where matters more loyalty transfer processes on supranational authorities in deepening European integration through the gear effect (spill-over effect).

In the 1970s, neo-functionalism and precepts found reflection, when European institutions seem to have lost their dominant role, influence and power of initiative in dealing with the Member States.

Neo-functional theses and arguments were challenged by neorealists and neorationalists, including intergovernmentalism considering in the integration process that the Member States are key stakeholders and are expected to achieve these priorities. Effects, which marked the integration

process, were reflected in the 1980s of the Single European Act and the intergovernmental conferences of the early 1990s that led to the Treaty of Maastricht. The events that conducted to European community development in these years were generated, at the same time, with the emergence of neo-federalist counterarguments.

Paradigmatic intergovernmentalist-supranational dichotomy generated disputes in the European integration process between the neorealist and neo-functionalist theory. The effects refer on attention to actors and institutions at different levels in terms of drafting legislation and policies. This is inducing to multilevel governance within the European Union that comprise different actors at supranational, national and sub-national levels, public and private actors in the complex system of European governance.

The institutionalist approach (with primary role in the political process) and neo-institutional approach model (existence of clear distinctions at institutions, conventions, rules, procedures, political and legal instruments) took effect on decision-making, the effects of these decisions and the powers of the European institutions.

A special role is played by federalist European integration model that seems to be animated by the economic crisis lately, on the one hand. On the other hand, it seems to be validated by the unity in diversity and the principle of subsidiarity.

Perhaps other variants of theories on supra-intergovernmentalist dichotomy are about to occur, since the integration process is developing⁷.

Whatever type of integration theory, promoted at one time or another in the history of European construction, dimensions of European integration process included economic integration, political integration, information integration, security integration, cultural integration, which are in the regulatory acts of integration European⁸.

⁷ I. Horga and A. Landuyt (2013): 25

⁸ V. Cucerescu (2013): 25

Multilevel Governance: From Cohesion Policy to Decision-Making Model

Multilevel governance is the theory that originates in the European integration process and studies on it. Gary Marks and Liesbet Hooghe developed the concept of multilevel governance in the early 1990s. Multilevel governance theory emerged as a result of studying the new institutional system of the European Union, enshrined in the Treaty of Maastricht. Multilevel governance articulates the idea that there are several interacting authorities in decision-making process. The transfer of powers is achieved by the Member States not only at the supranational level (*up*), but also at regional and local levels (*down*). Multilevel governance, being polycentric, designates dispersion of decision-making powers from local to supranational level. The concept of multilevel governance is a study subject of several areas, such as European studies and decentralization, federalism and international order, public policies and horizontal governance (public-private actors), local governance and transnational governance.

Originally the concept of multilevel governance emerged as a European policy, subsequently to be applied in decision-making process, regarding concerted cooperation between national, supranational and local actors. Multilevel governance was defined as “a system of continuous negotiation among nested governments at several territorial tiers”⁹. Multilevel governance theory emphasizes complex interactions between different actors. Public and private institutions are mobilized in EU cohesion policy in particular and EU policies in general. Thus, multilevel governance generated more interrogations on the role, place and powers of the Member States in the European integration process.

Multilevel governance in the European Union can be understood as a complex system of powers between the various levels of governance:

- exclusive competence – only the European Union is competent to act (Art. 3 TFEU);

⁹ G. Marks (1993): 403

- shared competence between the Union and the Member States – the European Union and the Member States may adopt binding acts in related fields; however, they may act only if the European Union chooses not to do (Art. 4, TFEU);

- competence to support, coordinate or supplement the actions of the Member States – in these areas, the European Union cannot adopt legally binding acts that would require the Member States to harmonize their laws and regulations (Art. 6 TFEU).

In practice, multilevel governance in the European Union means participation and coordination between all levels in the decision-making process and in the implementation and evaluation of policies.

The European Union can be characterized by cooperation between the Member States, intergovernmentalist classical supranational integration, since national governments have lost their exclusive authority in decision-making, sharing it with supranational institutions and private actors, thereby generating different levels of governance.

The European Union is a highly developed form of this system that can be considered a prototype of the postmodern state or postmodern state associations. In this system, the Committee of the Regions plays a prominent role alongside with other institutions in multilevel governance of the European Union.

Committee of the Regions

The Treaty of Lisbon is an important step towards institutional recognition of multilevel governance in the way the European Union works. Multilevel governance strengthens the powers of local and regional authorities whose influence grows in decision-making. The Treaty of Lisbon enshrines the territorial dimension of the European Union, namely territorial cohesion as part of the process of European integration. The Treaty of Lisbon defines precisely the role that is played by the Committee of the Regions

Committee of the Regions was created in 1994 as the voice of regions in the European Union. It has 353 members of regional and locally elected

representatives from the 28 Member States. The commissions cover competences in the following policy areas: employment, vocational training, economic and social cohesion, social policy, health; education and culture; environment, climate change, energy; transport and trans-European networks; civil protection and services of general interests. Committee of the Regions brings citizens closer to the European Union, because about 70% of EU legislation has a direct regional and local impact, EU citizens must be involved in the construction of the European Union, half of EU citizens believe their locally and regionally elected representatives are in a better position to represent them at the EU level, regional and local elected authorities close to citizens should be able to communicate their views during the preparation of the EU legislation. Committee of the Regions is guided in its activities by three fundamental multilevel governance principles:

- **subsidiarity**: decisions in the EU must be taken as close as possible to the citizens; the EU level must not take any action which could be carried out more efficiently by the national, regional or local authorities; the Committee of the Regions has the right to bring an action before the Court of Justice of the European Union if this principle is breached (this right is enshrined in the Treaty of Lisbon);

- **proximity**: all levels of governance must be “close to the citizens”; transparency in the work of national, regional and local authorities is essential to ensure citizen participation in the democratic process;

- **partnership**: the four levels of governance – EU, national, regional and local – cooperate closely to ensure good European governance; these four levels of governance are indispensable and must be involved throughout the decision-making process.

Usually the Committee of the Regions has 6 plenary sessions a year, adopts more than 50 opinions a year on EU legislation, organizes more than 40 stakeholders’ consultations each year and contributes to more than 300 events a year¹⁰.

¹⁰ Committee of the Regions, <http://cor.europa.eu/en/Pages/home.aspx>

One of the best referential books on EU multilevel governance – and the role of the Committee of the Regions – belongs to Beate Kohler-Koch and Fabrice Larat, *European Multi-level Governance: Contrasting Images in National Research*, published in 2009. Beate Kohler-Koch is Professor Emeritus of political science at Mannheim Centre for European Social Research (MZES), University of Mannheim, and former Coordinator of the Network of Excellence CONNEX. Fabrice Larat is Director of the Centre d'Expertise et de Recherche Administrative (CERA), Ecole Nationale d'Administration, France, and former Manager of the Network of Excellence CONNEX. The research on EU multilevel governance refers to three major issues: EU multilevel governance as a topic of research; reflecting the diversity of research traditions on EU multilevel governance; trends and patterns in research. The contributors illustrate that multi-level governance is a phenomenon perceived differently all over Europe. They observe distinct variations not only in the real-life impact of EU governance but also in different national research approaches, and showcase systematic empirical analysis of pertinent research projects across Europe. Recent advances in EU governance research form the basis for suggestions on how future research agendas could and should be directed. The book succeeds to capture in large how multilevel governance functions in the European Union, in which a major role is played by the Committee of the Regions. Now let us have a closer look to the results, which were attained by the Committee of the Regions.

The Committee of the Regions has established a system for monitoring compliance of multilevel governance in European policies and decision-making in the European Union.

Initially, the European Commission launched a vast reform of governance in order to drive forward a wide-ranging democratic process proposing four major changes: more involvement of citizens, more effective definition of policies and legislation, engagement in the debate on global governance, and finally the refocusing of policies and institutions on clear objectives. The initiative resulted in the white paper “European Governance” (2001). The structure of the white paper contains an executive

summary and four parts. In the executive summary it is stated that this paper “on European Governance concerns the way in which the Union uses the powers given by its citizens. Reform must be started now, so that people see changes well before further modification of the EU Treaties. The White Paper proposes opening up the policy-making process to get more people and organisations involved in shaping and delivering EU policy. It promotes greater openness, accountability and responsibility for all those involved. This should help people to see how Member States, by acting together within the Union, are able to tackle their concerns more effectively. (...) The White Paper is primarily addressed to them. (...) This should establish a basis for taking the governance agenda forward with the other Institutions”¹¹. The first part of the white paper answers the need to reform the European governance. The second part of the white paper identifies and defines the principles of good governance:

- *openness*: the European institutions should attach more importance to transparency and communication in their decision-making;
- *participation*: citizens must be more systematically involved in the drafting and implementation of policies;
- *accountability*: the role of each party in the decision-making process needs to be clarified. Each actor involved should then assume responsibility for the role given to them;
- *effectiveness*: decisions need to be taken at the appropriate level and time, and deliver what is needed;
- *coherence*: the EU conducts extremely diverse policies which need to be pursued coherently.

The third part advances proposals for change:

- *better involvement*: more openness in the way the European Union works, reaching out to citizens through regional and local democracy (participation by local-government associations in policy development, greater flexibility in the implementation of certain policies with a strong territorial impact, overall policy coherence), involving civil society, more

¹¹ European Governance – A White Paper (2001)

effective and transparent consultation at the heart of EU policy-shaping, connecting with networks;

- *better policies, regulation and delivery*: restoring confidence in expert advice, better and faster regulation – combining policy instruments for better results, simplifying Community law, better application of EU rules through regulatory agencies, better application at national level;

- the EU’s contribution to global governance;
- refocused policies and institutions.

The fourth part deals with provisions from governance to the future Europe: structure the EU’s relationship with civil society; make greater use of the skills and practical experience of regional and local actors; build public confidence in the way policy makers use expert advice; support the clearer definition of EU policy objectives and improve the effectiveness of EU policies; set out the conditions for establishing EU regulatory agencies; refocus the roles and responsibilities of each institution; a more targeted use by the Commission of its right of initiative; EU legislation which is stripped back to essential principles and a framework setting out how they should be implemented; The more effective involvement of national actors in the shaping, application and enforcement of Community rules and programmes; a reinvigoration of the Community method; dividing powers between the legislature and the executive; clear principles identifying how competence is shared between the Union and its Member States.

In fact, the White Paper on European Governance started a long lasting process on the future of governance in the European Union, which would comply with the heterogeneity of Europe’s peoples, make them a whole and imply them more in decision-making and law-making.

The *Own-Initiative Opinion* of the Committee of the Regions from the *White Paper on Multilevel governance* (2009) reads that the paper “reflects the determination to “Build Europe in partnership” and sets two main strategic objectives: encouraging participation in the European process and reinforcing the efficiency of Community action”. By this own-initiative, the Committee of the Regions “considers multilevel governance to mean coordinated action by the European Union, the Member States and local

and regional authorities, based on partnership and aimed at drawing up and implementing EU policies. It leads to responsibility being shared between the different tiers of government concerned and is underpinned by all sources of democratic legitimacy and the representative nature of the different players involved; recommends that each major Community strategic reform should be accompanied by a regional action plan agreed between the European Commission and the Committee of the Regions, setting out the political mechanisms to facilitate the ownership, implementation and evaluation of the policies adopted, and including a decentralized communication plan; establishing appropriate tools to support participatory democracy (...) development of (...) mechanisms, which are participatory and integrated mechanisms developing long-term strategic plans; recommends reinforcing the partnership practice, both vertically between “local and regional authorities – national government and European Union” and horizontally between “local and regional authorities – civil society”, particularly in the context of social dialogue; invites the Commission and the Member States to reform the open method of coordination to make it more inclusive, by developing participatory governance indicators and territorial indicators, in conjunction with regional and local authorities; recommends that the territorial impact analysis should become standard practice through the involvement, upstream of the policy decision, of the various actors concerned in order to understand the economic, social and environmental repercussions on the regions of Community legislative and non-legislative proposals; undertakes to submit proposals to support the use of experimentation at local and regional level in certain areas of intervention of the European Union, such as the strategy for growth and jobs, the social agenda, integration policy, innovation policy, cohesion policy, sustainable development and civil defence; recommends establishing European territorial pacts capable of bringing together, on a voluntary basis, the different competent tiers of government in order to adapt the implementation of the major political priorities and objectives of the European Union on a partnership basis with the local and regional authorities and invites local and regional authorities

interested in committing to such a process to indicate their interest as part of the consultation on the implementation of the White Paper”¹².

The White Paper on Multilevel Governance (2009) contains four major directions:

- building Europe in partnership,
- encouraging participation in the European process,
- reinforcing the effectiveness of Community action,
- implementing and monitoring the White Paper.

The White Paper on Multilevel Governance (2009) recognizes in the *Introduction* that governance is “one of the main keys to the success of the process of European integration. Europe will be strong, its institutions legitimate, its policies effective, and its citizens feeling involved and engaged if its mode of governance guarantees cooperation between the different tiers of government, in order to implement the Community agenda and meet the global challenges”¹³. Multilevel governance – as it is underlined – “serves the fundamental political objectives of the European Union: a Europe of citizens, economic growth and social progress, sustainable development, and the role of the European Union as a global player. It reinforces the democratic dimension of the European Union and increases the efficiency of its processes”¹⁴. Multilevel governance became a condition for European good governance, following those five principles of 2001 white paper: openness, participation, accountability, effectiveness and coherence.

Consequently, multilevel governance “ensures that these principles are implemented, maintained and enhanced. The implementation of multilevel governance depends on respect for the principle of subsidiarity, which prevents decisions from being restricted to a single tier of government and which guarantees that policies are conceived and applied at the most appropriate level. Respect for the principle of subsidiarity and multilevel governance are indissociable: one indicates the responsibilities of the

¹² See Own-Initiative Opinion (2009)

¹³ The White Paper on Multilevel Governance (2009): 3

¹⁴ *Ibidem*: 4

different tiers of government, whilst the other emphasises their interaction”¹⁵.

In building Europe in partnership, „the challenge of multilevel governance is to ensure that there is a complementary balance between institutional governance and partnership-based governance”¹⁶. In the same time it is highlighted that “multilevel governance represents a political “action blueprint” rather than a legal instrument and cannot be understood solely through the lens of the division of powers”¹⁷. Further it is mentioned that *in fact* “the conditions for good multilevel governance actually depend on the Member States themselves”¹⁸.

The *Assembly of European Regions Opinion on Multilevel Governance* (November 26, 2009) recognizes that the involvement of regional and local authorities as genuine partners in the EU multilevel governance system is a pre-condition to ensure the sustainable development of the Union and enhance its legitimacy. The Assembly of European Regions considers that multilevel governance is of relevance in the regional approach to the European neighbourhood policy.

Building a European Culture of Multilevel Governance: Follow-Up to the Committee of the Regions’ White Paper, having the opinion of the Committee of the Regions of 2012, establishes the general principles of multilevel governance, the means of consolidating the values and principles of multilevel governance for progress and strengthening (towards a new understanding of the principle of institutional balance, a partnership approach for smart regulation, a response to enhance citizens' ownership of European integration), transposing multiple governance into the European Union’s strategy and policy (the principle of multilevel governance as a guiding principle for all European policies and strategies with a strong regional impact, a new governance framework for European growth, implementing the Europe 2020 strategy and the seven flagship initiatives in partnership by means of territorial pacts, a new paradigm for future

¹⁵ Ibidem: 7

¹⁶ Ibidem: 5

¹⁷ Ibidem: 6

¹⁸ Ibidem: 7

cohesion policy, building the Single Market in partnership, the future environmental, climate change and energy policies, the future common agricultural policy, fisheries policy and maritime policy, implementation of the Stockholm Programme with local and regional authorities, multilevel governance mechanisms to support the EU enlargement strategy, a neighbourhood policy consolidated by multilevel governance, multilevel governance and globalisation: new developments likely), further stages in the implementation of multilevel governance.

The Resolution of the Committee of the Regions on Charter for Multilevel Governance in Europe of April 3, 2014, promotes the principle of multilevel governance, which is based on previous acts, recognizing the need for collaboration in partnership to solve the problems of European Union's citizens.

The Charter for Multilevel Governance in Europe consists of a preamble and two titles.

The preamble's provisions recognize the need to work together in partnership by cooperating better and running joint projects, considering interdependence, efficiency, multi-actorship in line with the principle of subsidiarity. In doing it the stress is on fundamental values, principles and principles, dialogue, coordination, joint commitment and transparency. Multilevel governance helps people to learn from each other, to experiment innovative solutions, to share best practices in the field in order to develop participatory democracy. The members of the Committee of the Regions accentuate that they stand for a multilevel-governance Europe "based on coordinated action by the European Union, the Member States and regional and local authorities according to the principles of subsidiarity, proportionality and partnership, taking the form of operational and institutional cooperation in the drawing up and implementation of the European Union's policies"¹⁹.

¹⁹ The Charter for Multilevel Governance in Europe. Preamble. <https://portal.cor.europa.eu/mlgcharter/Pages/MLG-charter.aspx>

The first title, Fundamental Principle, contains provisions on the principles of multilevel governance practices in Europe: transparency, openness, inclusiveness, participation, partnership, efficiency, coherence, synergy, subsidiarity, proportionality, and fundamental rights protection.

The second title, Implementation and Delivery, refers to making multilevel governance a reality in day-to-day policy-making and delivery: promotion of citizens' participation, close cooperation, fostering a European mind-set, strengthening institutional capacity building, and creation of networks at various levels.

The Charter for Multilevel Governance in Europe discloses that multilevel governance contributes to deepening European integration.

As a concluding example, Regulation (EU) No 1303/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 laying down common provisions on the European Regional Development Fund, the European Social Fund, the Cohesion Fund, the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development and the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund and laying down general provisions on the European Regional Development Fund, the European Social Fund, the Cohesion Fund and the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1083/2006 points to creating partnerships on the principle of multilevel governance according to Art. 5. The horizontal principles of the respective article stipulate that “the principle of partnership and multilevel governance shall be respected by Member States in order to facilitate achieving social, economic and territorial cohesion and delivery of the Union's priorities of smart, sustainable and inclusive growth. In order to respect those principles coordinated action is required, in particular between the different levels of governance, carried out in accordance with the principles of subsidiarity and proportionality, including by means of operational and institutional cooperation, with regard to the preparation and implementation of the Partnership Agreement and programmes”²⁰. So, we may find that

²⁰ Regulation (EU) No 1303/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 laying down common provisions on the European Regional Development Fund, the European Social Fund, the Cohesion Fund, the European Agricultural Fund for Rural

multilevel governance was originally planned as a European political cohesion and later became a guiding principle of good governance in the European Union. Moreover, multilevel governance is an inspiration for multilevel regulation.

Multilevel governance for associated countries: a scarecrow for politicians and redemption for citizens

Multilevel governance is a model that fits best the complexity of the European Union in terms of states and peoples as the European Union is neither a super-state nor a federation. According to the principle of conferral, the Member States grant certain competences to the supranational and sub-national levels. Although the European Union is very attractive from the economic point of view, politically it is a challenge for politicians of associated countries, especially for those of central authorities. In multilevel governance, the national parliaments and governments have to share their powers with supranational and sub-national authorities. Usually regional and local authorities are advantaged. Central authorities are not very eager to move quickly with the process of integration in the European Union.

Probably the best examples of such behaviour are Moldova and Ukraine. National politicians understand European integration as a tool of pumping money to be administrated more or less correctly by central authorities without any commitment to attain certain results timely. Ukraine's ousted president followed the idea that the European Union has to pay money in order his country to sign the Association Agreement. It is not yet clear if it was his plan or of the country that offered shelter for him.

As regards Moldova, despite of signing the Association Agreement with the European Union, politicians changed their minds in the result of cutting initial generous financial contributions, because of locally irresponsible use of money. *More for more principle* does not satisfy them. Moreover, the

Development and the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund and laying down general provisions on the European Regional Development Fund, the European Social Fund, the Cohesion Fund and the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1083/2006: 417

adequate rule of law scares them, because otherwise they would not be able dilapidate public money without any consequences for them. If they are to fight against corruption, it means that they have to fight against themselves. It is a suicidal act; so they decided to remain in a state of inertness so far. Thus, the parties act not like responsible parties for general interest, but like criminal gangs concerned with individual or group interests. Obviously, this state of affairs upsets citizens, on the one hand, and, on the other hand, the European Union as a party to the Association Agreement. In this case the same question arises: is it their plan or of the others?

Indisputably, multilevel governance for Moldova either inside or outside the European Union constrains politicians as they share their powers with other layers in the process of decision-making, reduces the authorities' abuses and considers the general interest of the citizens.

Conclusions

The European Union is built on the principle of conferral, which means that national authorities give certain powers to supranational authorities. This principle functions both “up” – the European Union – and “down” – regional and local communities.

The principle of unity in diversity cannot be attained outside multilevel governance in Europe, governance that implies various actors – supranational, national, regional, local or public and private ones. Otherwise European integration would not have been possible, because it needs legitimacy in order to exist. Interests of the European Union are to be represented duly, their voices are to be heard and taken into consideration, because the European Union is not a country, it is an association of free states and free peoples. The European Union is not created by sword, but by commitment of assumed democratic values, which paved the way for integration process. Europeanization is inherent to the integration process, seen as a set of common values that work for the benefit of European Union's citizens.

Thus, multilevel governance in the European Union has led to a renewed Europe, a pole of reference in terms of good governance. Multilevel

governance is possible in societies with a very high level of democracy. Multilevel governance generates total transparency and prosperous societies. Multilevel governance changes irrevocably joining countries for better. In the same time, multilevel governance can be considered a powerful instrument of European integration process, which assembles people and does not separate them. It is a clear response to the interrogation that they can be stronger together, can do more and better being united.

Multilevel governance is valuable for diversity of Europe, for the unity in diversity. Multilevel governance demonstrates the validity that diversity is sustainable in the process of European integration, because the European Union is a living societal body challenging state institutions, the political science and public administration. Ultimately, multilevel governance is a very good answer to representative authorities made *by* people and *for* people.

References:

Assembly of European Regions Opinion on Multilevel Governance. 26.11.2009

Building a European Culture of Multilevel Governance: Follow-Up to the Committee of the Regions' White Paper. 2012

Committee of the Regions. <http://cor.europa.eu/en/Pages/home.aspx>

Communication from the Commission of 25 July 2001 "European Governance – A White Paper". O J C 287/12.10.2001

Cucerescu V. (2013). *Drept institutional european*. Chisinau: Print-Caro

Horga I. and Landuyt A. (2013). *Communicating EU Policies Beyond the Borders*. Oradea: Oradea University Press

Ivan A. L. (2009). *Sub zodia Statelor Unite ale Europei – de la ideea europeană la Comunitățile Economice Europene*, Cluj-Napoca: CA Publishing

Kohler-Koch B. and Larat F. (2009). *European Multi-level Governance: Contrasting Images in National Research*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing

Marks, G. (1993). "Structural Policy and Multi-Level Governance in the EC", in Cafruny, A. and Rosenthal, G. (eds.). *The State of the European Community: The Maastricht Debate and Beyond*. Boulder, Colorado: Lynne Rienner, 391-411

Marks, G. and Hooghe, L. (1996). "European Integration from the 1980s: State-Centric v. Multi-level Governance". *Journal of Common Market Studies*. Vol.34, No. 3, 341-378

Marks, G. and Hooghe, L. (2004). "European integration and democratic competition". Friedrich Ebert Stiftung. 1-13.

<http://www.fes.de/euopolity/SummaryHoogheMarks.htm>

McCormick, J. (2008). *Understanding the European Union: A Concise Introduction*, London: Palgrave MacMillan

Regulation (EU) No 1303/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 laying down common provisions on the European Regional Development Fund, the European Social Fund, the Cohesion Fund, the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development and the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund and laying down general provisions on the European Regional Development Fund, the European Social Fund, the Cohesion Fund and the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1083/2006

The Resolution of the Committee of the Regions on Charter for Multilevel Governance in Europe of April 3, 2014.

<https://portal.cor.europa.eu/mlgcharter/Pages/MLG-charter.aspx>

Stubbs, P. (2005). "Stretching Concepts Too Far? Multi-Level Governance, Policy Transfer and the Politics of Scale in South East Europe". *Southeast European Politics*, Vol. VI, No. 2, 66-87

The White Paper on Multilevel Governance. 2009

Treaty on European Union. OJ C 191/29.07.1992

Wiener, A. and Diez, T. (2009). *European Integration Theory*. New York: Oxford University Press